

Induction of intelligence into molecules by using spinor radiation : An alternative to water memory

Alireza Sepehri and other researchers.

Abstract: By injection of a string of spinors within a molecule, it becomes sensitive to external magnetic fields. Because, a magnetic field could make all spinors parallel. According to the exclusion principle, parallel spinors repel each other and go away from each other. Consequently, they force on the molecular membrane and cause its growth. By removing external fields, this molecule return to its initial size. Injected string of spinors could be designed such as this molecule be sensitive only to some frequencies. Thus, a type of intelligence could be induced into a molecule such as it becomes able to diagnose special frequencies of waves and response. We test the model for milk molecules like fat, vesicles and microbial ones under 1000x microscope and observe that it works. Thus, this technique could be used in designing intelligence drug molecules. Also, this model may describe the origion of water memory.

Keywords: Intelligence, Spinor, Molecules, Milk, Magnetic Fields, Water Memory

I.Introduction

Intelligence is one of main puzzles which many researchers in different fields of science are working on it. There are various definitions for this word; for example, the capacity for logic, reasoning, planning, critical thinking and problem solving [1-3]. However, one of best definitions for intelligence may be a physical force which acts to maximize future of freedom [4]. This ability not only could be seen in animals but also, considerations show that plants have intelligence so [5]. Although, even cells and microbes may exhibit intelligence [6]. In addition to creatures, scientists believes that some machines also may obtain intelligence [7,8].

Now the question arises that if molecules like exosomes, vesicles and fat globules could obtain memory and intelligence? To response this question, we should note that even these molecules have no intelligence, we can induce some types of intelligent particles into them and make them clever. For example, we know that electrons response to magnetic fields and their spins become parallel to it. If we inject some spinning electrons into non-intelligent molecules, they obtain some signatures of intelligence. If these molecules become near a wire or any source of magnetic fields, their spinors become parallel. According to the Pauli exclusion principles, parallel spinors repel each other and force on the molecular membranes and structure to become more bigger. Thus, these molecules response to magnetic fields and grow. We can say that these molecules could diagnose the external fields and in response, they desire to become bigger. If we could engineer spinors within molecular structures, we can make them sensitive to special frequencies. In these conditions, molecules determine frequencies and response to some of them. This may be known as the first step of intelligence induction. Also, this model is in agreement with previous of observations of Montagnier group in bacterial waves [\[9,10\]](#).

From other side, this model may help us to understand the origin of water memory [\[11-14\]](#) . If micro bubbles of water contain some strings of electrons, they could response to external magnetic fields. Even, sometimes, these spinors may make a system which only absorb some frequencies of waves. Also, similar to quantum computers, spinors may store information of events and produce a memory.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we describe the method and consider the process of induction of intelligence into non-intelligent molecules. In section III, we bring results of some experiments which show how milk molecules could be sensitive to external fields and become intelligent. The last sections devoted to discussion and conclusion.

II. Material and method:

A. Material:

Materials in this research are: Different milk molecules like fat molecules, vesicles, exosomes, microbes, EM Generator, Electrodes, 1000x microscope

B. Method:

In this research, first, we induce some spinors like electrons within the milk molecules and put them under 1000x microscope. Spins of electrons should be in opposite directions. Because, according to the Pauli exclusion principles, parallel spinors repel each other and anti-parallel spinors attract each other (See Figure 1).

To induce spinors into a milk molecule, we could put it between two electrodes with negative and positive charges and turn on generator. In these conditions, electrons move from negative plane to positive one and confront with the milk molecules. Consequently, electrons collide with molecular structure, destroy it and enter within the molecules (See Figure 2).

To induce spinors into bacteria, we could use two electrodes which are connected to positive and negative ends of a generator. Although, many types of bacteria and microbes could not bear electrical currents and disappear. However, sometimes a string of spinors form within the structure of milk bacteria (See Figure 3).

A milk container could include different molecules. For example, fat molecules, bacteria, vesicles and exosomes are some of these molecules. All of these molecules could obtain charge and spin (See Figure 4). To induce spinors like electrons within these molecules, we can put them between two electrodes with opposite charges. In these conditions, electrons move from a negative electrode to positive one and penetrate into molecular membranes (See Figure 5).

When spinors enter into the structure of milk molecules, their arrows should be in opposite directions with respect to each other. Otherwise, according to the Pauli exclusion principle, they repel each other. However, any external magnetic field like the wire or molecular one could cause that spinors become parallel with respect to each other and that field. Consequently, parallel spinors repel each other, go away and molecules become big (See Figure 6). This could be a type of intelligence which molecules could diagnose external fields.

Figure 1. Induction of spinors and electrons into the milk fat molecules

Figure 2. A circuit for inducing electrons and other spinors within the milk fat molecules

Figure 3. Induction of electrons and other spinors into the milk bacteria and microbes.

Figure 4. Spinning milk molecules including fat, vesicles and bacteria

Injection of charged particles and spinors into the milk molecules

Wire

Electrodes

Figure 5. Injection of electrons and other spinors into the milk molecules

Figure 6. Near any magnetic field, spinors which were induced into milk molecules become parallel, repel each other and make big molecules

II. Results:

A Milk container includes many microbes which live freely (See Figure 7). However, after an electromagnetic radiation, most of them couldn't bear external fields and disappear. For this reason, most of molecules which are seen after radiation, may be fat molecules, exosomes or vesicles and some types of bacteria and microbes (See Figure 7). After putting the milk container between electrodes, some molecules become charged and spinning more faster. These molecules attract some smaller molecules and induce spin and charges into their structures (See Figure 8).By passing time, smaller molecules attract spinors. These spinors are anti-parallel and size of molecules doesn't change at first stages (See Figure 9). Eventually, spinors within the structure of molecules become parallel respect to the magnetic fields of electrodes, other molecules and each other. These parallel spins repel each other and cause to the growth of the size of molecules (See Figure 10). After removing magnetic fields of big molecules and electrodes, first molecules are big (See Figure 11). However, by passing time, spinors within their structures become anti-parallel and molecules return to their initial size (See Figure 12). These molecules are active and any external magnetic field cause that spinors become parallel and repel each other. Consequently, when spinors go away from each other, force on the structure of molecules and cause to their growth. Thus, a type of intelligence occurs within molecules. This means that after inducing spinors, molecules could diagnose radiation and maybe determine frequencies of waves. Then, by arranging spinors in special manner, one can design molecules such as they response only to some frequencies.

Figure 7. Milk microbes under 1000x microscope

Figure 8. Milk molecules after first radiation under microscope. It seems that some microbes were killed and only fat molecules are remained.

Figure 9. Emergence of first charged molecules and induction of spinors within other molecules under 1000x microscope

Figure 10. Spinning molecules experience external magnetic fields and grow under 1000x microscope.

Figure 11. Big spinning and charged molecules cause to the growth of other milk molecules under 1000x microscope.

Figure 12. After removing external magnetic fields, molecules return to their initial size and conditions.

Discussion

In this research, we have shown that by inducing spinors within biological structures, we can control them. These molecules could have their normal size, however, by applying an external magnetic field, their sizes grow. We can use of these active molecules in curing or controlling diseases like tumors. For example, we can send some of these molecules near a tumor and active them by waves. By growing their sizes, a pressure is applied to tumor structure and destroy it. Maybe, we could arrange spinors which molecules become sensitive to some special frequencies of waves. For example, these molecules could become active only for frequencies of tumors. These molecules could be known as intelligent drug molecules.

From other side, this model may describe the origin of water memory so. If micro/nano water bubbles contain some spinors, they could response to external magnetic fields. Also, similar to quantum computers, spinors within bubbles could save information and consequently, a memory is appeared.

Conclusion:

In this research, we have tested a model to induce a type of intelligence into molecules. This intelligence is appeared by injection of a string of spinors within the structure of molecules. These molecules are able to diagnose special frequencies and waves and become big. This is because that spinors become parallel respect to external magnetic fields. According to the Pauli exclusion principle, parallel spinors repel each other, go away, force on the structure and cause to the growth of the size of molecules. By designing special strings of spinors, we can create an intelligence such as molecules only response to some special frequencies. We can use of these intelligent molecules for controlling diseases like tumors. These intelligent molecules may include water bubbles so. Thus, this model could propose good reasons for the emergence of memory within water bubbles.

References:

[1] Humphreys , L.G (1979)." The construct of general intelligence".
Intelligence. **3** (2):105-120. doi:10.1016/0160-2896 (79)90009-6.

- [2] Colom, Roberto (December 2010)."Human intelligence and brain networks"*Dialogues Clin.Neurosci.* **12** (4):489-501.doi:10.31887/DCNS.2010.12.4/rcolom.
- [3] Salovey, Peter; Mayer, John D (March 1990)." Emotional Intelligence".*Imagination, Cognition and Personality.* **9** (3) : 185-211. doi:10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDG.
- [4] Wissner-Gross, A.D.; Freer, C.E. (19 April 2013)."Causal Entropic Forces".*Physical Review Letters.***110** (16):168702. doi:10.1103/Phys.Rev.Lett.110.168702
- [5] Goh, C.H.; Nam, H.G.;Park,Y.S.(2003)."Stress Memory in plants ".*The plant journal.* **36** (2) :240-255.doi:10.1046./j.1365-313X.2003.01872.x
- [6] Brian J.Ford (December 2017). "Cellular Intelligence:Microphenomenology and the realities of being ". *Progress in biophysics and molecular biology.* **131**:273-287.doi:10.1016/j.pbiomolbio.2017.08.012.
- [7] Russell, Stuart J.; Nor in, Peter (2003)." Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach". Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Apprentice Hall. ISBN. 978-0-13-790395-5
- [8] Scassellati, Brian (2002)." Theory of mind for a humanoid robot ".*Autonomous Robots.***12** (1):13-24.doi:10.1023/A:1013298507114.
- [9] Montagniet, L.;Aïssa, J.; Ferris, S.; Montagnier, J. L.; Lavallée, C. (2009). "Electromagnetic signals are produced by aqueous nanostructures derived from bacterial DNA sequences". *Interdisciplinary Sciences: Computational Life Sciences.* **1** (2): 81–90. doi:10.1007/s12539-009-0036-7
- [10] Montagnier, L; Del Giudice, Emilio; Aïssa, Jamal; Lavallee, Claude; Motschwiller, Steven; Capolup

o, Antonio; Polcari, Albino; Romano, Paola; Tedeschi, Alberto; Vitiello, Giuseppe (2015). "Transduction of DNA information through water and electromagnetic waves". *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*. **34** (2): 106-112. arXiv:1501.01620. doi:10.3109/15368378.2015.1036072

[11] Benveniste, J; Jurgens, P; Hsueh, W; Aissa, J (January 1997). "Transatlantic Transfer of Digitized Antigen Signal by Telephone Link". *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*. **99**(1): S101–S200. doi:10.1016/S0091-6749(97)81064-0.

[12] Benveniste, J; Aissa, J; Guillonnet, D. "The molecular signal is not functional in the absence of "informed" water". *FASEB Journal*. **13** (4): A163.

[13] Igor Jerman, Romana Ružič, Rok Krašovec, Metod Škarja & Lea Mogilnicki (2005) Electrical Transfer of Molecule Information into Water, Its Storage, and Bioeffects on Plants and Bacteria, *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*, 24:3, 341-353, DOI: 10.1080/15368370500381620

[14] Igor Jerman, M. Berden & R. Ružič (1996) Biological Influence of Ultraweak Supposedly EM Radiation from Organisms Mediated Through Water, *Electro- and Magnetobiology*, 15:3, 229-244, DOI: 10.3109/15368379609012879